

Appendix A

Supplementary information: Chapter 2

A.1 Properties of materials

Table A.1 Curve fit parameters for thermal conductivity of brass (W/m·K) from NIST [162]. The fit is valid for temperatures between 5–116 K with an equation range of 5–110 K. The curve fit error is 1.5% relative to the data.

Coefficient	Value (W/m·K)
<i>a</i>	0.021035
<i>b</i>	-1.01835
<i>c</i>	4.54083
<i>d</i>	-5.03374
<i>e</i>	3.20536
<i>f</i>	-1.12933
<i>g</i>	0.174057
<i>h</i>	-0.0038151
<i>i</i>	0

The thermal conductivity is calculated using the following curve fit:

$$\begin{aligned}\log_{10}y = & a + b(\log_{10} T) + c(\log_{10} T)^2 + d(\log_{10} T)^3 \\ & + e(\log_{10} T)^4 + f(\log_{10} T)^5 + g(\log_{10} T)^6 \\ & + h(\log_{10} T)^7 + i(\log_{10} T)^8\end{aligned}\tag{A.1}$$

$$y = 10^{\log_{10}y}\tag{A.2}$$

where T is the temperature in K and y is the thermal conductivity in W/m·K.

Table A.2 Interpolated thermal conductivity of structural SiC at selected cryogenic temperatures based on digitised data from [163]. Values are given with an uncertainty range corresponding to ± 2 K.

Temperature (K)	κ_{\min} (W/m·K)	κ_{\max} (W/m·K)	κ_{avg} (W/m·K)
7	1.00	2.60	1.80
28	12.53	16.00	14.27
30	14.24	17.78	16.01
33	16.89	20.49	18.69
35	18.68	22.29	20.49
40	22.59	26.32	24.46
45	26.13	29.82	27.98
56	32.63	36.10	34.36
77	43.47	46.58	45.03

Table A.3 Estimated constant-volume heat capacity C_v of bulk 3C-SiC at cryogenic temperatures, extracted from digitization of Figure 5(a) in [253]. The original data represents specific heat per Si–C pair, which is equivalent to per mole of SiC. This is appropriate for modelling solid-state heat transfer in the packed bed OPC-reactor, as the SiC particles used are dense (30–50 mesh) and not porous, making bulk lattice heat capacity the dominant contribution.

Temperature (K)	C_v (J/mol·K)
29	0.95
30	1.05
31	1.15
32	1.25
33	1.35
34	1.45
35	1.55
36	1.65
37	1.75
38	1.85
39	1.95
40	2.05
44	2.50
45	2.65
46	2.80
55	3.90
56	4.10
57	4.30
76	6.95
77	7.10
78	7.25

Table A.4 Estimated constant-pressure heat capacity C_p of IONEX[®] at cryogenic temperatures, approximated using experimental data for maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃) from digitisation of the heat capacity curve reported in Figure 1 of the study [236]. IONEX[®] is assumed to be a dense, magnetically susceptible iron oxide, and maghemite is selected as a proxy due to its similar physical and magnetic properties. The extracted values are appropriate for packed-bed thermal modelling under the assumption of bulk solid behaviour.

Temperature (K)	C_p (J/mol·K)
29	8.5
30	8.9
31	9.3
32	9.7
33	10.1
34	10.5
35	11.0
36	11.5
37	12.0
38	12.5
39	13.0
40	13.5
44	15.5
45	16.0
46	16.5
55	20.0
56	20.5
57	21.0
76	27.5
77	28.0
78	28.5

Table A.5 Estimated constant-pressure heat capacity C_p of 70/30 brass at cryogenic temperatures, extracted from [231]. Values were digitized from a graphical source and converted from cal/g·K to J/kg·K. A ± 1 K uncertainty band is included based on curve slope. The conversion used is 1 cal/g·K = 4,184 J/kg·K.

Temperature (K)	C_p (J/kg·K)	Uncertainty (± 1 K)
28	40.2	± 3.8
30	47.7	± 3.8
35	65.3	± 4.2
40	82.4	± 4.2
45	98.2	± 4.2
56	131.6	± 4.2
77	176.0	± 4.2

A.1.1 Bed porosity (void fraction) of the catalyst bed

The porosity (void fraction) of the IONEX[®] catalyst was experimentally determined using a simple volumetric displacement method. A 3mL sample of dry catalyst was weighed in a graduated cylinder. Deionised water was then added to the same volume mark (3mL), and the cylinder was reweighed to determine the volume of water required to fill the interstitial voids. The void fraction, ε , was calculated using the ratio of the water volume to the total catalyst volume:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{V_{\text{water}}}{V_{\text{cat}}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

This measurement was repeated twice, yielding void fractions of 0.642 and 0.560, with a standard deviation of 0.041. These values are consistent with typical porosities for packed beds of irregular granular media [137].